

Scientific approaches to pedagogical competence in developed countries.

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Annotation.

Over the following decades, the higher education system began to be radically reformed in a number of European countries, the USA, Russia and in our country. At the same time, the main attention is paid to the formation and improvement of students' competence in the specialty they acquire. Nowadays, society needs a specialist in a completely new guise. He should grow up to be an active creative thinker, researcher, specialist, independently seeking scientific information and applying it in his practical activities.

Keywords: pedagogy, education, upbringing, competence, cooperation, technology, professional competence, innovation, national pedagogy, scientific research.

On the issue of approach from the point of view of pedagogical professional competence, scientific discussion and debate continues among scientists and specialists from all over the world. In relation to pedagogical scientists from the United States and European countries, it is clear that Russian scientists have left much for issues of professional competence. V.Slastenin, I. Chapter 3 of the teaching manual "pedagogy", written by Isaev and others, is dedicated to the "professional competence of the educator"[1], giving ideas about this concept and skill. The authors note that the profession of a pedagogical competence system, practical and theoretical training, professional competence of an educator has a managerial and formative character. Management of personality formation requires competence. This in itself demonstrates the professional skills of the teacher, concentrating on his theoretical and practical training. In the direction of one profession or another, they write that the qualification classification of a teacher is measured by the norms of the model of pedagogical competence. V.A.Bolotov and V.V. According to the Serikov, from the point of view of competence, the approach shows not the student's erudition, but the ability to solve problems and assesses it as a necessary ability at the very first level.[2] Ye.V. Bondorevskaya and S.V. Kulnevich believes that the elements of competence that students collect in their scientific work should be directed or necessary only to the main goal, to conduct pedagogical activities.

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The main goal of education forms in the student socially necessary qualities and competence, self-awareness as a person, constant improvement of their knowledge, self-control

and activation. Of course, we can see the degree of study of this topic in scientific research carried out by many foreign and higher and specialists in our country. If we want to take a look at the activities of the US higher pedagogical education system, B.D.Woolfson, T.N.Kurilova, Z.A.If we want to know the scientific work of Malkova and others about the goals of us pedagogical education, N.D.Nikandorova, V.Ya.Pilipovsky, G. on professional pedagogical education of future teachers.G.Agapova, O.O.Borovikova, V.S.About the work of Budenko and others, and about the system of professional development of us teachers V.B.Gargay, N.I.When we look at the work of Kustinova and others, it is desirable. From the scientific work of the scientists mentioned above, we can imagine that the educational system of Russia and the United States is enriched by complementing each other. It is noticeable that a continuous system of pedagogical training has been created in the USA, Canada, Australia and a number of European countries, and they are widely studying this problem in a certain system. On the issue of the philosophical foundations of competency approach in the United States, the authors who reflected their global goals and objectives, organizational system, essence, standards of education, quality control of education, the activities of higher pedagogical schools M.Apple, D.Armstrong, D.L.Ball, D.Barnes, F.Baumgartner, M.Cochran-Smith, D.K.Cochan, L.Darling-Hammond, S.Feiman-Nemser, A.D.Glenn et al.[4]

The implementation of the tasks set out in the national program of Personnel Training in our country puts new requirements on a modern teacher. The question of what a modern teacher should look like comes to the first level. In terms of competence, the issue of approach is not approached as blindly as in foreign countries. Instead of professional competence, the concept of professional competence is given by creative teams and pedagogical scientists, aimed at developing methods and techniques for teaching a particular field and Sciences in basic scientific work, but it is precisely the approach to the issue of a competency teacher that is just being implemented. The organization and implementation of the educational process at the level of professional development of the system of continuous education of our country is not able to use the current requirements of the perspective of the current period as well as effectively as practical teachers. The main reasons for this lie in the fact that the problems of professional development are not sufficiently researched, only a small number of scientists focus on the approach in terms of competence. B. in issues of professional development problems and professional competence in our republic.Adizov, A.A.Ahmadov, A.X.Aminov, T.L.Khurvalieva, N.A.Muslimov, Sh.Scientists such as saidkulov are conducting scientific research. These studies mainly study organizational pedagogical issues and pedagogical diagnostic issues of improving the system of professional development. While scientists from the Institute of retraining pedagogical personnel named after Abdullah Avlani reflect on the concept of competence and its types using the secular experiments we mentioned above, T.L.Khurvalieva proposes to study professional competence in types. It is recommended to study it by dividing professional competence, professional competence into stages of formation, personal competence, universal competence and specific types of competence. More from the materials of Russian pedagogical scientists, especially A.V.Khutorsky attempts to apply them directly to the Uzbek pedagogical system, citing the classification of seven competencies of the teacher in education. In this regard, on April 10, 2013, an international conference called "pedagogical-psychological problems of the secondary specialized vocational education system" was held.

T. At this conference.Abdullaev, Z.Ismailova" pedagogical-psychological problems of changing the thinking of pedagogical personnel", N.Abdullaeva "development of creative thinking

potential of students", N.A.Muslimov, O.A.Putsinov” formation of professional-creative competence in the process of Professional Education Teachers 'Professional Development", F.Mirzaeva "features of professional training of a pedagogical person", Q.Olimov, K.All articles other than his scientific articles “Razvitie professionalnoy kompetentnos ti sostavlyayushaya pedagoga” Umatalieva teaching methods and methods, the dedication of various disciplines and specialties to the traditional scientific theories of teaching technologies and pedagogy is visible. Hence, in terms of competence and competence, a system of separate studies of approach issues is being implemented very slowly. Taking this into account, it is worth noting the need for in-depth study of the issue of improving the competence of the teacher of Higher Education based on the requirements of the National Program of Personnel Training of the Respublika of Uzbekistan, and a lot of scientific work should be carried out.

Aspects of the formation of teacher professional competence

The goal of the National Training Program is to radically reform the educational sphere, to fully resolve it from the ideologies and upheavals left over, to create a national system of highly qualified training of personnel that meets high spiritual and moral requirements at the level of developed democratic states.

The educator is responsible to the Society for educational and educational work in his specialty. He must have the right to teach, teacher, teacher, teacher, educator, educator, educator, or, more precisely, the owner of professional competence, in conjunction with the improvement of his professional training on a regular basis. Now there is little for the teacher to master the practical and theoretical knowledge of the profession, science, specialty of his choice. He should be able to apply new methods and techniques of education in any situation in his activities, in a word, be the owner of competence.

The concept of” competence”, an approach in terms of competence, the owner of competence, to dwell on the content of these Terms, first of all, we will focus on the national traditions and values in this regard, which have been formed over the centuries. If in our country any professional owner began to master his profession and teach it to his students, then they began to add the term of this profession to his name. Mosh healer, Omon healer, Obogul Potter, Latif Barber, Murodjan hofiz, Mamatoy blacksmith or Mamatoy aka knives etc. This recognition testifies not only to the fact that this person has a certain profession, but also to the fact that the inhabitants of a higher territory are engaged in any profession, having achieved such recognition through their high success. Chust knives, Chust doppelgänger, Rishton Potters, Urgut Potters, Samarkand bakers, breads, etc. It is certainly not difficult to notice that this is competence, to say with the recognition, authority, trust – amanational and scientific language that has been given to a person or professional owner or team who has been serving abroad for many years without interruption. The same can be said about folk art, but the rise of the profession to a higher level is a higher qualification – skill than competence. Abdurahim Dorboz, Tursunboy polwon, Mamat the teacher, Mamat domla, etc. As we comment on the concept of "competence", we focus on the meaning and essence of the term. Competency is a Latin word meaning “worthy”, “proper” or “appropriate” in Uzbek. One can understand that one is a person worthy of overcoming simple and complex issues by applying his knowledge, skills and practical experiences. In many cases, the term “professional competence” is used. It can be understood as the ability to successfully apply their practical experience, knowledge and skills in the implementation of their professional duties. Competence is the term of jurisprudence. It is the rights and duties that fall under the authority of a specific body or person and determine the place of this person in the state and public system. In

terms of the content of jurisprudence, competence includes the following elements: promoted objects (territories, phenomena, actions, are held within a certain framework), the sum of the rights and duties, powers that a particular body and individual can apply for their activities. Competence (social law). This is precisely the authority of a subject, which is established by law for management processes, and a certain social task will be assigned to this authority. Competence management authority. This is considered a personal vocalization of a specialist (employee) in solving certain professional tasks. Cross-cultural competence. The ability to successfully find a language with other culture nomoyanda lari. The main competence of the organization. Being a factor in ensuring the competitive tolerance of the organization, it is considered the main support tool in the competitive struggle. Competence area. Consisting of the sum of knowledge and skills of an individual or team, they carry out their task within a higher and more competitive framework.

In the Russian-Uzbek dictionary published by the Academy of Sciences of Uzbekistan in 1983, "kompetentnost" was translated into Uzbek as "possession of deep knowledge", "foundation of deep knowledge", "awareness", "omilkor lik". "Kompetentny" - a competent, well-educated person with sufficient education, a competent person with competence, has the right to consider the issue, is translated in meaning. "Competence" is given in concepts such as area or Matter, law, or discretion in which any person is aware[5]. Academy of Sciences of Uzbekistan A.S. The concept of "competence" is not entirely included in the two-Tom "Explanatory Dictionary of the Uzbek language", published in 1981 by the Pushkin Institute of language and literature. In general, in our country, the approach to any field, in particular, pedagogical activity in terms of competence, began to be applied for the next five years. Approached in terms of specific morphological and semantic features of the Uzbek language, it is desirable that the terms and concepts of "competence" are used in a close sense to the Latin words "competere" – "worthy", "competo" – "worthy" or "I will achieve". According to the Uzbek Alphabet, which is based on the Latin script, we want to express the opinion that the use of the word "competence" in all meaningful cases avoids many confusion. It follows from this that from the point of view of competence, it is advisable to apply the approach, that the team or person in question is the owner of such competence, and finally, the owner of pedagogical professional competence. Thus, in any case, competence determines the place of a particular person or community in society. Strengthens it with both legal and moral attitudes. Any group, community or individual in a society is formed as the owner of competence in its field with high qualifications and knowledge in a particular field, and regularly improves this competence. This issue is approached in the interests of society. The individual, on the other hand, fulfills his or her life interests above all by perfecting his or her competence while achieving the level of demands society puts on the individual. We have proposed combining the concepts of "competence" and "competence" that scientists around the world recommend above. Analyzing scientific work on the approach from the point of view of competence, we clearly notice that different opinions are being expressed about these two concepts. A.G. In Bermuda's view, "competence unites all the senses, knowledge, experience, in general, the whole being of an improving individual into a single system". "Competence is not only the fact that an individual is knowledgeable, but also constantly updates his knowledge," says M.A. Choshanov. M. In Aronov's opinion, competence indicates that the specialist is ready for a certain activity. The ability to function in uncertain situations is competence, says O. Ye. Lebedev.[6]

Competence is based on the intellectual personal, social professional life activity of a person, writes I.A. Zimnyaya. A.V. Khutorsky believes that the concepts of "competence" and

competence " can be distinguished as follows. Competence is a qualitative and effective activity in the attitude of an individual towards something and processes within a certain framework, being considered a continuum of personal qualities (knowledge, qualifications, experience, methods of activity). Competency, on the other hand, means that a person has the sum of competencies that are in demand, expressing his personal attitude towards the types of activities. As can be seen from the above, a number of controversies continue over the issue of competence over its place in society. In the field of education, the awareness of the main elements of universal competence is one of the most fundamental problems of modern pedagogy. In the case of basic competence, there is a wide variety of opinions on the application of the experience of Educators of the world or on the setting of competence criteria based on the norms of traditional Uzbek pedagogy, only those issues that have not yet been solved. A. Pedagogical scientist of the Avloni Institute for teacher training L.T. Khurvalieva describes: " competence – knowledge, skills, competence, views, value and personal qualities of the individual, the manifestation or ability to influence Qualification " [7]. Education is the main condition and pledge of human perfection and prosperity of the nation. Educational processes are a nationwide issue of state control. In our country, education, that is, teaching, is carried out in harmony with upbringing. While the National Training Program requires a radical improvement in the educational process, it is conspicuous that the training of competent educators is also approached based on these requirements. Competence or extreme skillfulness, the training of highly qualified educators has become the most pressing issue of our time, and, it is permissible to say, the most fundamental task of the state and society. As we noted above, pedagogical activity is close to the side of artists and scientists in terms of their functions in society and depending on the characteristics of professional quality, and on their psychological principles. The features of pedagogical labor are designed to educate and educate a person. The formation of human qualities in young people, the human calculation of the subject of Labor and its influence on the person who controls society require self-competence. The ancient Greek philosopher Plato said that " if the poor man is a bad master, then the state will not lose anything much from this, but only the people will dress worse. If the youth educator does his job badly, then a category of ignorant, ignorant, ignorant and stupid will arise in the country." President Of The Republic Of Uzbekistan I.A. Karimov said that " the training of mature, qualified personnel in all respects should be the main condition of our program". Higher education institutions in the decision of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan on measures to further improve the system of training and training of pedagogical personnel, the higher education system sets the task of organizing the main scientific methodological Center for the retraining of pedagogical and managerial personnel and their professional development. The main scientific methodological center is tasked with the development of general educational programs, educational and regulatory materials for retraining and improving pedagogical personnel of higher educational institutions using modern methodologies based on the study of the results of work on ensuring the level of professional training of professors and teachers, the required level of training and training of highly qualified personnel. In the same decision, the assessment of the activities of teachers in accordance with modern requirements, the development of educational and methodological materials and effective methodologies for teaching foreign languages and information and communication technologies are established. It also organizes seminars and trainings in regional centers and network centers on these directions; the following are: enterprises of our country equipped with advanced, modern equipment and technologies in various sectors of the economy in order to ensure the improvement of the content of educational programs in the relevant educational disciplines, integration of

education with production; priorities for the development of educators in modern science achievements, related specialties; in order to familiarize them with the effective methods of conducting scientific research, the scientific expert develops programs for cooperation with research institutions (scientific institutions of the Academy of Sciences, Network scientific research institutes, centers, laboratories, etc.) and their use as base facilities for retraining educators and improving their skills; coordinates the activities of regional and network centers; organizes and conducts training courses of In accordance with this decision, proposals to re-train pedagogical personnel and improve their skills will be satisfied with the creation of 5 regional centers, the establishment of 10 network centers, professional development under higher education institutions and the completion of educational institutions and faculties. So, from the decision of the Cabinet of ministers, state sponsorship of improving the professional competence of the teacher of the school of higher education is visible. At this point, we found it necessary to express our suggestions and comments on the implementation of this decision. The main scientific methodological center regional and network centers is a legal entity. A certain amount of fees are being introduced for qualification services. This can of course create economic difficulties for some skilled teachers. Summarizing all organizational issues, we would propose as follows:

- the teacher of Higher Education, who has successfully graduated from regional and network centers, should be involved in training on the basis of a state grant to the main scientific methodological Center.

- for a certificate of pedagogical professional competence, it should be stipulated that the exam test will be passed.

- * for certified teachers, benefits should be provided on scientific research, pedagogical activity.

- four areas specific to professional competence for testing and evaluation exams are taken as the basis of darkor: a) theoretical and practical knowledge of the specialty; B) pedagogical skills; g) personal qualities; d) worldview. Thus, having a pedagogical professional competence and obtaining a certificate confirming this competence will create opportunities for the teacher to grow further, improve his knowledge, work on shi, inspire confidence and confidence in his profession. As we have noted above, competence, especially since professional competence are signs of the place of the individual in society, Society will also be interested in training professionals with highly qualified professional competence. Abdullah Avloni, one of the founders of national pedagogy, in his work "Turkic Gulistan yohud ethics" of moral-didactic content, divides the hulks into good and evil, making modernity the main criterion, proving his reasoning with the thoughts of Hippocrates, Pluto, Aristotle, Saadi Sheroziy and Beatil[8]. Adib considers the love of the motherland, to fight for it, from the best human hulks. "The homeland is the city and country where everyone was born and raised, it is necessary to appreciate, Love, Live," he says. In his writings, Abdullah Avlani touched on education and said, "Education is either a matter of life, or of momot, or of salvation, or of destruction, or of happiness, or of disaster for us". Education is the main condition and guarantee of human perfection and prosperity of the nation, a nationwide issue under the control of the state and society, the purpose and function of which is perfect human education, education is indiscernible harmony.

Summarizing the above points, we see that an equal half of the essence of pedagogical professional competence is formed by educational relations. The most important duty of an educator to society, the result of his activities is the perfect human education.

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